

IN SEARCH OF VIABLE PEDAGOGY IN CHEMISTRY THAT COULD IMPROVE STUDENTS' SELF-CONFIDENCE: A CONSIDERATION OF PREDICT-OBSERVE-EXPLAIN-ELABORATE-WRITE-EVALUATE (POE₂WE) OR DISCUSSION STRATEGIES?

By

Victor Oluwatosin Ajayi, PhD & Christina Tanko Audu²

¹Department of Science and Mathematics Education, Benue State University, Makurdi, Nigeria

²Department of Integrated Science, College of Education, Zing, Taraba State, Nigeria

Corresponding Email: drvictorajayi@gmail.com; +2348034012521

Abstract

The study investigated if a Predict-Observe-Explain-Elaborate-Write-Evaluate (POE₂WE) or discussion strategies is a viable pedagogy in chemistry that could improve students' self-confidence in Ekiti State, Nigeria. The study adopted quasi-experimental research design. The instrument used for data collection was Chemistry Self-Confidence Scale (CSCS). Cronbach Alpha was used to ascertain the reliability index of CSCS which gave reliability value of 0.89. The target population of this study was 14,753 which was the population of senior secondary 2 students offering Chemistry in the study area. A sample of 156 students comprising 84 boys and 72 girls drawn from 6 schools within 6 Local Government Areas (LGA) out of 16 LGA in the Ekiti State, Nigeria selected using multi-stage sampling techniques. Two research questions and two null hypotheses guided the study. The research questions were answered using Mean and Standard Deviation scores while the null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance using Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA). The study revealed that POE₂WE strategy significantly improved students' self-confidence [$F_{1, 156}=255.284, P<0.05$] than discussion method. It was also found that there was no significant interaction effect of treatments and gender on the mean self-confidence [$F_{1, 156}=.085, P>0.050$] of students in Chemistry. It was recommended that since POE₂WE strategy was found to be effective strategy for improving students' self-confidence in Chemistry; Chemistry teacher's trainee should be trained on the use of POE₂WE strategy and serving teachers should use it. The curriculum developers should use POE₂WE to develop and refine the Chemistry curriculum.

Keywords: Predict-Observe-Explain-Elaborate-Write-Evaluate (POE₂WE), discussion strategy, chemistry and students' self confidence

Introduction

Chemistry is a very important subject as its knowledge is required for the successful study in many important professions. Chemistry occupies a pride of place in the senior secondary school curriculum. The specific objectives to be achieved for Chemistry in the curriculum as stated in the report of Nigerian Educational Research and Development Council, (NERDC, 2012) includes: providing the students with basic knowledge in chemical concepts and principles

through efficient selection of content sequencing; showing inter-relationships between Chemistry and other science subjects; and providing a reasonable and adequate foundation for a post-secondary school Chemistry course. It is therefore necessary that students studying Chemistry should understand the subject so that they can apply the knowledge to everyday interactions with people and the ever changing environment. Despite the importance of the knowledge of Chemistry to the society and the efforts of researchers to improve on its teaching and learning, The researchers observes that, students' self-confidence in solving chemistry related problems is low.

This low self-confidence in solving chemistry related problem is also attested to by the West African Examination Council (WAEC) Chief Examiners' report (2017/2018) on Chemistry result who reveals that students are weak and don't usually answer questions on some aspects of chemistry such as hydrocarbon, isomerism, alkanes, alkenes, alkynes, benzene, carbon, and nuclear chemistry due to low self-confidence or trust in their abilities which in turn affect their academic performance. The low self-confidence of students in solving chemistry related problems has affected the educational pursuits and aborted the ambition of many candidates who aspire to study professional courses such as Medicine, Pharmacy and Chemistry. This students' low level of self-confidence appears to have persisted which is often blamed on poor teaching methods. By implication, poor strategy to teaching invariably translates to students' low self-confidence in solving chemistry related problems which in turn affect their performance.

Self-confidence is an individual's characteristic which enables the individual to have positive or realistic views of him/herself or the situations that he/she is in (Al-Hebaish, 2012). Self-confidence can be explained as an individual's expectation of his or her ability to achieve a goal in a given situation and is a very influential factor in ensuring that a person's potential is realized. In other words, individuals with high self-confidence may have a realistic view of themselves and their capabilities which makes them to be persistent in their endeavours. Ajayi (2019) opines that learners who possess high self-confidence are likely to perform well in school due to the belief they have in themselves. Whereas, learners with low self-confidence may be reasonably thought to be prone to uncertainty, insecurity, anxiety and social distance which can affect their academic performance or success in life generally. In this study, self-efficacy belief is Senior Secondary 2 students' confidence or trust about their ability to solve Chemistry related problems using Predict-Observe-Explain-Elaborate-Write-Evaluate (POE₂WE) or discussion strategies as expressed in scores in this study.

According to Ahmed (2016), student's low self-confidence that he or she has the ability needed to complete the cognitive-ability test or task has also been attributed to the ineffective teaching methods adopted by teachers. Hence, developing lessons using innovative strategy that involve students' active participation when engaging in chemistry activities is anticipated to uplift self-confidence to solve chemistry related problems. Predict-Observe-Explain-Elaborate-Write-Evaluate (POE₂WE) is associated with meaningful and mastery learning. They enable students to identify the major concepts and relate them to the concepts in their existing knowledge structure (Kinchin, 2013). The learner therefore plays an active role in knowledge construction, which leads to meaningful learning. POE₂WE is a learning strategy developed to know student understanding on a concept with constructivist approach. This model constructs knowledge with orderly process in terms of prediction solutions, conducting experiment to prove prediction, explaining experimental results in spoken or written texts, making an example of its application in daily life, recording discussion results and making an evaluation about students understanding in orally and textually. The learning phases of POE₂WE strategy is explained as follows:

Phase 1: Predict

After presenting students with all the relevant background information, students predict what they think will happen next. It is important that they actually commit this to paper, so that they can't "wiggle out" of their prediction at a later stage if they find out they were wrong.

Phase 2: Observe

After prediction has been recorded, students observe what happens next. In a scientific experiment this may involve closely watching what happens and recording any key information such as measurements.

Phase 3: Explain

Explanation comes after observation, and it is here that students who have predicted wrongly need to wrestle with their internal assumptions that led them astray (these may be unconscious, and hence need drawing out first). For those who predicted correctly, they may still have had incorrect assumptions, so this is important to keep in mind (watch out for students with correct answers but low confidence).

Phase 4: Elaboration

Elaboration phase deals with students who make an example or apply the concept in daily life. It is adapted from constructivist approach. In this phase, teachers encourage students to apply a

new concept in a new situation, so they more understand the concept. This phase is the development of elaboration phase in the constructivist approach.

Phase 5: Write

Write phase is to do written communication, reflecting student knowledge and ideas. Writing can help students to express their knowledge and ideas. Students write discussion results and answer questions in Student Worksheet. Besides, they make the conclusion and report from the experiment result.

Phase 6: Evaluation

Evaluation phase is an evaluation on student knowledge, skills, and thinking process changes. In this phase, students are evaluated in terms of straight movement material orally and textually. This phase is a development of the constructivist approach.

Pajares and Urdan (2014) and Gassner (2015) noted that individuals with low self-confidence tend to avoid tasks that they think or believe they do not have the capabilities to accomplish those specific tasks. Studies by Nana, Sajidan, Akhyar and Rochsatningsih (2014) Gernale, Arañes and Duad (2015) reports that students improved significantly in their learning outcome in Physics and Elementary Basic Science respectively when taught using Predict-Observe-Explain-Elaborate-Write-Evaluate (POE₂WE) compared to those taught using conventional lecture method. Similarly, Demircioğlu, Demircioğlu and Aslan (2017) concluded that Predict-Observe-Explain enhance significantly students' achievement in Biology than when taught using modified lecture method. In the light of this trend of diverse results in the general findings of several studies, there is need to search for viable pedagogies that could improve students' self-confidence in Ekiti State, Nigeria. Hence, is POE₂WE strategy or Discussion strategy viable Chemistry pedagogy?

Research Questions

The following research questions guided this study:

1. What is the difference in the mean self-confidence scores between students taught chemistry using Predict-Observe-Explain-Elaborate-Write-Evaluate (POE₂WE) and those taught using discussion method?
2. What is the mean interaction effect of treatments and gender on students' self-confidence Chemistry?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses guided the study

1. There is no significant difference in the mean self-confidence scores between students taught Chemistry using Predict-Observe-Explain-Elaborate-Write-Evaluate (POE₂WE) and those taught using discussion method.
2. There is no significant interaction effect of treatments and gender on the mean self-confidence scores of students in Chemistry.

Methodology

The design for this study was quasi-experimental, non-randomized control group pretest and posttest design. There was no randomization of subjects so as not to disrupt the school programme. This research was carried out in Ekiti State, Nigeria. A sample of 156 students comprising 84 boys and 72 girls drawn from 6 schools within 6 Local Government Areas (LGA) out of 16 LGA in the Ekiti State, Nigeria selected using multi-stage sampling techniques. Two research questions and two null hypotheses guided the study. An instrument known as Chemistry Self-Confidence Scale (CSCS) was used for data collection. CSCS was a researcher made 20 items questionnaire which is intended to help students express their confidence in solving Chemistry related problems. Each of the items is a 4-point Likert-rating scale with 4 response options. The options are Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D), and Strongly Disagree (SD).

The items were developed from information acquired through review of relevant literature by the researcher. However, standardized tests do have environmental, regional and sociological sensitivity the items were face validated by presenting them to three experts in Science Education and one lecturer that is knowledgeable in test and measurement in the Department of Curriculum and Teaching, Benue State University, Makurdi. The experts were asked to assess the instrument in terms of scope of coverage, content relevance, ambiguity, and vagueness of expression. Corrections and suggestions arising from these experts were used to review the instrument and the instructional packages. Chemistry Self-Confidence Scale (CSCS) upon validation was trial-tested to establish the reliability of the instrument. Cronbach Alpha was used to ascertain the reliability index of CSCS which gave reliability value of 0.89.

Before the commencement of the actual treatment, the researcher used one week for the training of the Chemistry teachers who served as research assistants. Intact classes were assigned to experimental and control groups after which Chemistry Self-Confidence Scale (CSCS) was

administered as pre-test by the researcher with the assistance of the sampled schools Chemistry teachers. This lasted for one week before actual teaching commences. During lessons, the teachers taught the experimental group I Chemistry topics using Predict-Observe-Explain-Elaborate-Write-Evaluate (POE₂WE) strategy while the control group were also taught the same chemistry topics using discussion strategy in line with lessons procedure prepared by the researcher. This lasted for six weeks. At the end of these actual teaching periods, the pre-CSCS was reshuffled and administered as post-test which lasted for one week and the post test was marked by the research assistants using the marking scheme developed by the researcher. The pre-test score constituted the covariant of the post-test scores. Mean and Standard Deviation scores were used to answer the research questions while Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) was used to test the null hypotheses.

RESULTS

Research Question One

What is the difference in the mean self-confidence scores between students taught chemistry using Predict-Observe-Explain-Elaborate-Write-Evaluate (POE₂WE) and those taught using discussion method? The answer to research question one is contained on Table 1.

Table 1: Mean Self-Confidence and Standard Deviation Scores of Students Taught Chemistry using POE₂WE and Discussion Strategy

Group	N	PRE- CSCS		POST- CSCS		Mean Gain within Group
		\bar{x}	δ	\bar{x}	δ	
POE ₂ WE	77	1.29	0.18	3.82	0.21	2.53
Discussion	79	1.30	0.17	1.98	0.19	0.68
Mean diff. between Groups		-0.01		1.84		1.85

Source: Field Survey, 2020

Table 1 reveals the mean critical thinking and standard deviation scores of students taught Chemistry using Predict-Observe-Explain-Elaborate-Write-Evaluate (POE₂WE) and discussion method (DM). The data in Table 1 show that the overall mean difference between students in POE₂WE and discussion strategy groups was 1.85 in favour of POE₂WE. This implies that students in POE₂WE group had higher self-confidence than students in discussion group.

Research Question Two

What is the mean interaction effect of treatments and gender on students' self-confidence Chemistry? The answer to research question two is contained on Figure 1.

Covariates appearing in the model are evaluated at the following values: TprCSCS = 1.3418

Fig 1: Interaction plot of treatments and gender on students’ self-confidence in Chemistry

Figure 1 presents a graph of the interaction effect of treatments and gender on the mean self-confidence scores of students in Chemistry. The graph lines for gender did not intercept which suggests that interactive effect of treatments and gender on students’ self-confidence in Chemistry was very minimal.

Hypothesis One

There is no significant difference in the mean self-confidence scores between students taught Chemistry using Predict-Observe-Explain-Elaborate-Write-Evaluate (POE₂WE) and those taught using discussion strategy. The data analysis of Table 2 is used to explain hypothesis 1.

Table 2: Two-Way ANCOVA for Mean Self-Confidence Scores of Students Taught Chemistry using POE₂WE, and Discussion Strategy

Source	Type III sum of squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected model	192.673 ^a	4	32.112	1001.321	.000	.952
Intercept	69.528	1	69.528	2168.028	.000	.878
TPrCSCS	.094	1	.094	2.919	.089	.010
Group	189.421	1	94.710	2930.001	.000	.912
Gender	.001	1	.001	.032	.858	.000
Group*Gender	.030	1	.015	.305	.542	.003
Error	9.653	151	.032			
Total	3452.457	156				
Corrected Total	202.326	155				

a. R squared = .959 (Adjusted R Squared= .958)

Source: Field Survey, 2020

Table 2 presents the ANCOVA result for mean self-confidence scores of students taught Chemistry using Predict-Observe-Explain-Elaborate-Write-Evaluate (POE₂WE) strategy and discussion strategy. The data in Table 2 reveal that there is significant difference in the mean self-confidence scores between the students taught Chemistry using POE₂WE and those taught using discussion method in favour of POE₂WE [$F_{1, 155}=2930.001$, $P<0.05$]. Hence, the null hypothesis that there is no significant difference in the mean self-confidence scores between students taught Chemistry using Predict-Observe-Explain-Elaborate-Write-Evaluate (POE₂WE) and those taught using discussion method was rejected. This means that POE₂WE significantly enhanced students' self-confidence in Chemistry compared with discussion strategy. Meanwhile, the effect size was 0.912 which is considered as large effect size. This implies that, 91.2% of the difference in the self-confidence scores between the groups was explained by the treatments. Hence, the difference in the self-confidence scores between students taught using POE₂WE and those taught the groups has a large statistical effect size.

Hypothesis Two

There is no significant interaction effect of treatments and gender on the mean self-confidence scores of students in Chemistry.

The data analysis of Table 2 is used to explain hypothesis 2. The table presents a two-way ANCOVA for self-confidence of students taught Chemistry using Predict-Observe-Explain-Elaborate-Write-Evaluate (POE₂WE) and discussion strategy. The table also presents the interaction effect of instructional strategies and gender. The data in Table 2 reveals that there is no significant interaction effect of treatments and gender on the mean self-confidence scores of students in Chemistry [$F_{1, 155} = .305$, $P>0.050$]. The null hypothesis is therefore not rejected. Meanwhile, the effect size was 0.003 which is considered as very small effect size. This implies that, only 0.3% of the interaction in the self-confidence scores between the groups was explained by treatments and gender. Hence, the interaction of treatments and gender on students' self-confidence has very small statistical effect size.

Discussion of Findings

The main focus of this study was to investigate if a Predict-Observe-Explain-Elaborate-Write-Evaluate (POE₂WE) strategy or discussion strategy is viable pedagogy in chemistry that could improve students' self-confidence in solving chemistry related problems. The findings of this study revealed that students taught Chemistry using POE₂WE Strategy had significantly higher self-confidence than their counterparts taught using discussion method. This is in line

with Gernale, Arañes and Duad (2015) and Teerasong, Chantore, Ruenwongsa and Nacapricha (2016) findings that students improved significantly in their achievement in Elementary Basic Science and Physics respectively when taught using POE₂WE strategy compared to those taught using conventional teaching method. In another related study, Demircioğlu, Demircioğlu and Aslan (2017) investigated the effect of Predict-Observe-Explain (POE) on the understandings of grade II biology students about osmosis. Though the strategy used did not emphasize the important of students' elaboration-writing-evaluation. Yet, the finding of study revealed that, POE significantly enhanced students' understandings than traditional teaching method. The likely explanation for this outcome may be connected to the fact that the POE₂WE strategy helped the learners to possess a meaningful in-depth knowledge of the content area by finding out their initial ideas and motivating them to want to explore the concept and generate investigation when compared to the discussion method. POE₂WE strategy helps students to learn meaningfully because it focuses on linking students existing ideas and beliefs relevant to a situation and exploring the appropriateness of these ideas and beliefs.

The study revealed that the interaction effect between strategies and gender on the self-confidence of students in Chemistry is very minimal but ANCOVA test shows that the interaction effect was not significant. This implies that there was no significant interaction between strategies and gender on mean self-confidence scores of students in Organic Chemistry. Hence, POE₂WE strategy can be used successfully irrespective of gender in fostering students' self-confidence than the use of discussion strategy. Treatment interaction according to Ajayi (2019) generally implies that different learners with different characteristics may profit more from one type of instructional method than from another and that therefore it may be possible to find the best match of learners' characteristic and instructional method in order to maximize learning outcomes. In this case, there is no need for separation of instructional strategy for male and female students, since POE₂WE strategy could be used successfully for the two groups.

Conclusion

It is evident from the findings of this study that the use of POE₂WE enhanced students' self-confidence in Chemistry than the use of discussion method. In the same vein, there was no interaction effect between treatments and gender on students' self-confidence in Chemistry. This implies that there is no need for separation of instructional strategy for male and female since POE₂WE strategy could be used successfully to improve both male and female students' self-confidence than discussion strategy.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made:

1. Chemistry teacher's trainee should be train on the application of Predict-Observe-Explain-Elaborate-Write-Evaluate (POE₂WE) and serving teachers should employ the use of POE₂WE strategy in teaching to improve students' self-confidence in Chemistry.
2. The curriculum developers should use POE₂WE strategy to develop and refine the Chemistry curriculum.
3. PEOE and VH instructional strategies are not gender sensitive therefore both male and female students should be involved in POE₂WE activities to enhance their self-confidence in Chemistry.
4. Ministry of Education, school administrators and professional bodies such as Association of Science Educators (ASE) and Science Teachers Association of Nigeria (STAN) should organize conferences or seminars and workshops to popularize and sensitize Chemistry teachers on the integration of POE₂WE instructional strategy in teaching Chemistry.

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